

Anti-woman Religions and Woman-centric Paganism

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Feminism

Feminists argue that women are not treated on par with what they deserve. Their status in the society is still degraded and minimized within the societal norms of family and its invisible handcuffs. Women are looked upon as inferior to men, indeed. Feminists accuse the age-old dominance of the men-folk of being responsible for female subservience to men; It has been pointed out by most feminists that the masculine world cannot justify it's being regarded as the very type of humanity and that women seen as relative to men.

Language as a tool

In short, the patriarchal world misrules its better half and feminism represents one of the most important, social, economic, aesthetic revolutions of modern times. Female subservience, in my opinion, has its roots in almost all religions and the literary history that followed. As to the English Language, terms like humanity, human resources and chairman do exhibit strong notion of patriarchy, though these terms supposed to denote the entire understanding. Only after a long-fought struggle waged by the western feminists, the common-non-sexist terms 'humanity', 'personnel,' and 'chairperson' came into being. 'Ms' is being used as an equivalent to 'Mr.', instead of 'Mrs.' 'which is to be firmly condemned as a sexist term.

What Religions say

Rig Veda: Women are not faithful.

Manu Dharma: Woman is undeserved to enjoy freedom. She is greedy and treacherous.

Buddha: Women ought to be ashamed to show their face before men.

Christianity: Woman is created for man. She shall abide by the wishes of her husband, revering him a God.

Islam: Women shall practice 'purdah.' They should not go out on their own without the company of their male guardian.

Jain scriptures: Woman with her body cannot attain salvation.

Religions, in short view women as mere tools that have been created for the sole purpose of entertaining and making men happy.

of course, there was a time when women were treated on par with men. Women too were hunters then. Civilization flourished with agriculture, and a land-owning class emerged. Wealth brought out changes in man, and each man wanted to make sure that his biological children alone inherit it. As a consequence, morality as an inherent quality was made mandatory for women.

Role of Great People

Some great people looked upon women in high esteem. According to Swami Vivekananda, “Society is like a bird, and men and women are its wings. If one wing is damaged, the bird cannot fly”. To the tremendous poet-philosopher Khalil Gibran, “Women opened the windows of my eyes and doors of my spirit. Has it not been the woman-mother, the woman-sister, and the woman-friend, I would have been sleeping among those who seek the tranquility of the world with their snoring”. To quote the ex-prime minister of India, Mrs. Indira Gandhi, “Humanity is deprived of half its energy and creativity if the women are neglected.” But these voices sound in vain with the well-settled notions of religions in India.

Mother India

In the Indian context, women are brainwashed for long, to blindly go after many religious customs, never realizing the right intention and core of religions which have always joined hands against them. The women representation in the parliament of independent India is still less than 8%, and it is less than 6% in the Lok Sabha. The women representation in our Supreme, as well as High Courts, is less than 4%. Women working as administrative heads are less than 3%. This great country’s agricultural sector efficiently employs and exploits 80% of the women-folk whose labor is unrecognized and underpaid. Data collected by NGO’s clearly show that equal wage for equal work remains a dream. In other sectors, too, the labor of women is underestimated. The literacy of men in India is 65.5, whereas, in women, it is only 50%. Every 3 minutes, a woman falls victim to sexual violence and degradation; young girls, aged women, and even children are not spared. We listen to people of prominence advising us, women-folk, to behave modestly and take care not to induce our Adams towards evil ideas like the silly-Eve. But yes, our prime minister has, to his credit a thoughtful comment, ‘Parents ought to control boys. Boys are to be taught to behave themselves and to respect women.

Women on Board

In Big Divas connection with women are still not on board, an extensive report by leading law firm Khaitan & coin, international network of learned women titled ‘Women on Boards’: A Process, Policy and Implementation Road map found that, among the 1,470 public classified companies in India, the number of women managers on board were 350, serving only 4% of the total number of independent filmmakers on board. The report found one-fifth of the world’s 200 largest companies have no women directors. The largest economies- the U.S, China, and Japan which have no quotas for women in board rooms, had the lowest growth of women on boards, suggesting that unless pushed, change does not occur, the report said.

Administrative Position

Number Chancellor	-	3
Vice-chancellor	-	12
Pro-Vice-chancellors	-	3
Registrars	-	7
Deans	-	72
Directors	-	11

*Women Administrators in Indian Universities.

Breaking Down Barriers for Gentlewomen in the Workplace

“With economic models straining in every corner of the world, none of us can afford to perpetuate the barriers facing women in the workplace” Secretary of State Hillary Clinton at the new APEC Women’s Summit in San Francisco.

According to researcher Kristen Schilt, men force have the most to say regarding those barriers-in particular, the men who know how women are treated in the workplace from firsthand expertise.

Schilt’s research investigates the world of work, as seen through the participation of transgender men. Take Thomas, for illustration. When Thomas replaced Susan at trial, a man going at an associated company told Thomas’s boss that it was good to move to fire Susan, due to her inexperience, but that the “new guy”(Thomas) was excellent. What the work associate did not recognize was that Susan has transitioned to enhance Thomas at the industry.

In other word, Susan and the “new guy” was the same person with the same skills and abilities. As Schilt describes it, many Trans men “moderate being treated as not just different from women but better than women” at work.

A case study on gender-related barriers – Questionnaire

Do you feel inferior as a woman?

Do you have decision making power?

Do you balance your role at the workplace and home?

Are you comfortable with your colleague men?

Who do you like your superior to be?

Is your labor recognized at the workplace?

Do you face pressures at the workplace?

Do you receive the same dignity and respect enjoyed by men in society?

What according to you, is the most significant barrier for women at the workplace?

Suggest st overcome these barriers.

100% of women answered that they never feel inferior to women. To all the questions they pointed towards the patriarchy that still prevails in the society. All of them claimed that they work hard in vain. All of them unanimously agreed that they never receive the same dignity and respect enjoyed by men in society. Few felt that women themselves are enemies to the other women.

An Analysis arrived based on a Questionnaire given to 25 women faculty members at Selvam College of Technology, Namakkal is given below.

71.4% of women firmly believe that they are not given the same respect and dignity as that of men.

24% believe that they are respected according to personal reasons like power and wealth.

4.6% of women believe that men are more skilled.

The repressed cry of the women-folk all over the world is in existence. Rajam Krishnan, renowned Tamil writer, and activist once expressed her anguish to a young writer thus. “Reasons which transformed me into a feminist 50 years ago, to fight for the rights of women-folk are still seen around, and now you people are continuing my struggle. I do not know whether this would come to an end.

Paganism

On the contrary to most religions, the age-old ‘Paganism’ of Europe tends to have had certain lofty ideals about the status of women in particular. Paganism dates back to the worship of Mother Goddess that was in practice for many decades and ceased to exist with the advent of organized Christianity. The novel Da-Vinci-code written by Don Brown brings forth the historical conspiracy against women through the clues left by the legend painter Leonardo-da-Vinci, who, the book claims o be a Pagan worshipper.

Paganism is a religion invented in the course of the second to third centuries AD; is a broad group of indigenous and historical polytheistic religious traditions- primarily those of cultures known to the classical world. Pagans generally believe that divinity is found in mind and nature. By the late half of the 4th century in the Greek-speaking East, pagans were- paradoxically –most commonly called Hellenes. ‘Hellenes’ or “gentile” (ethnos) remained the word for “pagan.” Nature generally, and Agrarian, in particular, had been the characteristic of paganism.

As for women, the promiscuity, which is the surest sign of her degradation, never existed as a general or stable characteristic of primitive folk. In ancient Egypt her position was far higher than in late; it was high too among the Teutons. The glimpses we have of ancient matriarchates speak much for the older, honorable position of women; their peculiar festivals (as in Greece, of the Thesmophoria and Arrephoria; in Rome, of the BonaDea) and certain worships, as of the local Korai or Isis. Women priests and women-centered customs were prominent. Paganism revered Motherhood and speaks of love for mother.

Neopaganism

Some currents of Neopaganism, inappropriate, Wicca, have a ditheistic concept of a single goddess and an only god, who in his games represent a united whole. Polytheistic reconstructionists focus on reconstructing polytheistic religions, including the various goddesses and figures associated with indigenous cultures.

The term theology is sometimes used in the context of the Neopagan Goddess movement, a pun on theology and “goddess” intended to intimate a feminist approach to theism.

The Goddess movement is a loose grouping of social and religious phenomena that grew out of second-wave feminism, predominantly in North America, Western Europe, Australia, and New Zealand in the 1970s, and the spiritual center as well. Spurred by the insight that women were not treated equitably in many religions, some women turned to a Female Deity as more in tune with their spiritual needs. Education in the Arts became a vehicle for the study of humanitarian philosophers like David Hume at that time. A unifying theme of this diverse movement is the femaleness of Deity (as opposed and contrasted to a patriarchal God).

It is quite interesting that the male-dominant west had had touches of eastern religions in which ‘Mother Goddess’ has a vital role. ‘Paganism is all in praise of the virtuous feminine. If read completely. Paganism is undoubtedly knowledge with new dimensions to the present-day feminism while challenging all existing religions in this regard.

To conclude, ‘Paganism’ which held a woman in high esteem, revered her as Goddess should take over the patriarchy to ensure that women enjoy their deserving status and of course what the constitutions of men of all nations have guaranteed them for namesake. It is the high time women should realize the conspiracy of all religions against them in double-crossing women’s rights and equality, which are yet to be implemented.

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